

Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 2,11-dimethyl-3,12-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,10,13-tetraazacyclooctadeca-1,3,10,12-tetraene

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Abstract : Complexes of the types [ML(NO₃)₂]NO₃ {where M = Cr^{III} or Fe^{III}}, [ML(NO₃)₂] {where M = Co^{II} or Ni^{II}}, [CuL]Cl₂ and [ZnLCl₂] (where L = 2,11-dimethyl-3,12-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,10,13-tetraazacyclooctadeca-1,3,10,12-tetraene) have been synthesized by condensation of 2,3-hexanedione with 1,5-diaminopentane in the presence of metal ions as templates. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, electronic spectra, IR spectra and magnetic measurements. Zinc(II) complex has been characterized by ¹H NMR spectral studies also.

Keywords : Transition metal complexes, IR spectra, ¹H NMR spectra, electronic spectra, macrocyclic complexes.

Introduction

There has been considerable interest during the recent years in the synthesis of new macrocyclic ligand systems due to the enhanced kinetic and thermodynamic stabilities of their complexes as compared to their open chain analogues¹. Macrocyclic complexes are also of interest because of the synthetic flexibility involved in their preparation which allows for systematic variations in parameters such as ring size, the nature of donor atoms and the steric and electronic effects associated with groups located on the periphery of the macrocyclic ring – the ‘ligand suprastructure’². Complexes of the metal ions with synthetic macrocyclic ligands are also of great importance because of their resemblance with many natural systems e.g. porphyrins and corrins³. A large number of macrocyclic complexes have been synthesized by the condensation of α - or β -diketones with diaminoalkanes in the presence of metal ions^{4,5}. Curtis⁶ has prepared Ni^{II} complexes of *rac*- and *meso*-5,12-dimethyl-7,14-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,11-diene. Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with 1,5,9,13-tetraazabicyclo[7.7.3]nonadecane and 1,5,9,12-tetraazabicyclo[7.5.2]hexadecane have been reported⁷. However, metal complexes of tetraazamacrocycles with more than 16-membered rings have not been reported so far except

a few complexes of macrocycles derived from α - or β -diketones and diaminoalkanes reported earlier from our laboratories⁸⁻¹¹. In the present paper Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 18-membered tetraazamacrocyclic-2,11-dimethyl-3,12-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,10,13-tetraazacyclooctadeca-1,3,10,12-tetraene derived from 2,3-hexanedione and 1,5-diaminopentane are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of the metal ions with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,5-diaminopentane in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of the complexes of 18-membered tetraazamacrocyclic (Scheme 1).

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids and are stable at room temperature. On heating they do not melt but decompose at higher temperature (Table 1). They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, methanol, chloroform and acetonitrile but soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide. All of the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Conductances : Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO are recorded in Table 1. The Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes behave as 1 : 3 electrolytes indicating that two nitrates which are coordinated in solid state, are replaced by the solvent molecules. Molar con-

M	X	m	n	x
Cr	NO ₃	3	1	9
Fe	NO ₃	3	1	9
Co	NO ₃	2	0	6
Ni	NO ₃	2	0	6
Cu	Cl	2	2	2
Zn	Cl	2	0	0

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

also corresponds to 1 : 2 electrolyte. The molar conductance of Zn^{II} complex is very low showing it to be non-electrolyte.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectrum of chromium(III) complex exhibits bands at ~ 16530, ~ 25000 and ~ 27100 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ⁴B_{1g} → ⁴E_g(a), ⁴B_{1g} → ⁴E_g(b) or ⁴B_{2g} and ⁴B_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} transitions respectively¹⁴. The Fe^{III} complex shows three bands at ~ 13700, ~ 16400 and ~ 25000 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(D) transitions respectively¹⁴. The cobalt(II) complex exhibits bands at ~ 11000, ~ 16400 and ~ 19000 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}, ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively³. The nickel(II) complex exhibits bands at ~ 9800, ~ 16400 and ~ 27000 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively¹⁵. Positions of these bands are consistent with the distorted octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry. The Cu^{II} complex shows a characteristic band at ~ 16400 cm⁻¹ due to ligand field transitions¹⁶. Thus Cu^{II} complex may possess square planar geometry. All the complexes show intense charge transfer bands at ~ 29400 cm⁻¹ or above.

Infrared spectra : In the IR spectra of the macrocyclic complexes, no absorption band was observed at 1700 and

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of metal complexes of the macrocycle Me₂Pr₂[18]N₄tetraene (L)^a

Complex	Colour and decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Λ _m (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
			M	N	Cl		
[CrL(NO ₃) ₂] ₂ NO ₃	Grey (202–204)	82	8.56 (8.68)	9.42 (9.35)	–	91	3.81
[FeL(NO ₃) ₂] ₂ NO ₃	Brown (148–150)	35	9.37 (9.27)	9.18 (9.30)	–	102	6.16
[CoL(NO ₃) ₂]	Green (174–176)	42	10.94 (10.84)	10.41 (10.30)	–	55	4.75
[NiL(NO ₃) ₂]	Green 98	78	10.73 (10.80)	10.26 (10.31)	–	64	4.04
[CuL]Cl ₂	Green (101–102)	60	12.99 (12.83)	11.17 (11.31)	14.20 (14.32)	54	2.21
[ZnLCl ₂]	Off white (246–247)	64	13.26 (13.16)	11.10 (11.27)	14.07 (14.27)	17	Diamagnetic

^aThe N values do not include nitrate nitrogen which is removed on treatment with H₂SO₄ in Kjeldahl's method.

ductances of ~ 109 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMSO have been reported for 1 : 3 electrolytes¹². The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes suggesting that both the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by the solvent molecules¹³. The conductance value for Cu^{II} complex

3200–3400 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of unreacted >C=O or -NH₂ group¹⁷. All the macrocyclic complexes show medium to strong intensity bands in the region 1590–1620 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to the coordinated >C=N group. This shows that >C=O and -NH₂ groups

Fig. 1. 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum of [Zn(Me₂Pr₂[18]tetraeneN₄)Cl₂]

have condensed to give C=N linkage. For Cu^{II} complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-3,10-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraaza-cyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene, Coltrain and Jackels¹⁸ have reported $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})_{\text{sym}}$ band in the region 1585–1595 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})_{\text{asym}}$ band in the region 1602–1612 cm^{-1} . All the macrocyclic complexes containing nitrate exhibit absorption bands at 810–825 and 1380–1390 cm^{-1} due to ionic nitrate¹⁴. Bands at 1010–1040 cm^{-1} are due to coordinated nitrate groups and the appearance of the bands at 1500–1550 cm^{-1} confirms the monodentate coordination mode of nitrate group^{19,20}. In the IR spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, appearance of absorption bands due to coordinated as well as ionic nitrate indicates that the nitrate groups are weakly coordinated.

Magnetic moments : The observed values of μ_{eff} for the complex at room temperature (300 K) are given in Table 1. For the Cr^{III} complexes, the effective magnetic moment (3.81 B.M.) indicates the presence of three unpaired electrons and is consistent with essentially octahedral geometry for the chromium atom. The μ_{eff} value for Fe^{III} complex is 6.16 B.M. suggesting a high-spin state of Fe^{III} with five unpaired electrons. The Fe^{III} complex may possess octahedral geometry. Rana *et al.*¹⁴ have reported magnetic moments in the range 3.60–3.70 and 5.76–5.84 B.M. respectively for the Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of a macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine. For the Co^{II} complex the μ_{eff} value of 4.75 B.M. corresponds to a high-spin state of Co^{II} . The effective magnetic moment for Ni^{II} complex is 4.04 B.M. suggesting a high-spin state of Ni^{II} . This confirms the octahedral nature of the complexes evidenced by the electronic spectra. The Cu^{II} macrocyclic complex possesses magnetic moment 2.21 B.M. which corresponds to one unpaired electron. Higher values of magnetic moments for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes may be due to large orbital contribution. For Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of a macrocycle derived from dihydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine, magnetic moments have been reported in the range 4.48–4.65, 2.96–3.10 and 1.78–1.88 B.M. respectively²¹. The Zn^{II} complex is diamagnetic.

¹H NMR spectrum : ¹H NMR spectrum of Zn^{II} macrocyclic complex was recorded and is reproduced in Fig. 1. The $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons of the amine residue give a triplet

at δ 2.78 ppm due to coupling with the $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons. The $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ and $\gamma\text{-CH}_2$ protons of the amine residue give broad peaks at δ 1.62 and 1.48 ppm respectively. In macrocyclic precursor, 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, Fig. 2) the $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm and $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm²². The free macrocycle has not been isolated during the present investigations but it is expected to exhibit the $\alpha\text{-}$ and $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons almost at the same position as reported for KIM. As compared to KIM, in Zn^{II} complex of the macrocycle, peaks of $\alpha\text{-}$ and $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons are observed at higher field. This high-field shift of these protons confirms the coordination of the nitrogen atoms of the macrocycle to the zinc atom. The $\text{CH}_3^{(\text{a})}$ protons of the ketone residue give rise to a triplet at δ 1.05 ppm due to coupling with the $\text{CH}_2^{(\text{b})}$ protons and the $\text{-CH}_2^{(\text{c})}$ protons of *n*-propyl group give rise to a broad peak at δ 2.20 ppm and the $\text{-CH}_3^{(\text{d})}$ protons give rise to a singlet at δ 1.98 ppm. The peaks due to the $\text{-CH}_2^{(\text{b})}$ protons of the ketone residue merge with the peaks of -CH_2 (β and γ) protons of the amine residue.

Fig. 2. 1,2,8,9-Tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione.

Experimental

Materials and methods : $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ZnCl_2 (All Fluka), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck), $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH), 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich) and 1,5-diaminopentane (Aldrich) were used as supplied. *n*-Butanol was distilled before use. Chromium was determined volumetrically by potassium dichromate using diphenylamine as indicator. Similarly, iron content was determined in Fe^{III} complex after its reduction to Fe^{II} with stannous chloride. Copper was determined iodometrically using starch as indicator. Cobalt, nickel and zinc were determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange indicator for cobalt and Eriochrome Black T for nickel and zinc. Nitrogen was determined by

Kjeldahl's method. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl. Specific conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were measured at room temperature by a Systronics 304 direct reading conductivity meter. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO on a Jasco-7800 UV-VIS spectrophotometer at Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, Udaipur. IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (300 K) on a Gouy balance at Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali, Rajasthan, using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as a calibrant. ¹H NMR spectrum (DMSO-*d*₆) was recorded on a Bruker-300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as a reference at Biocryst Pharmaceutical Inc., Birmingham, Alabama (USA).

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : To a solution of Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (1.5 mmol, 0.6002 g in ~20 ml *n*-butanol), a solution of 2,3-hexanedione (3.0 mmol, 0.3424 g in ~15 ml *n*-butanol) was added with stirring. To this, a solution of 1,5-diaminopentane (3.0 mmol, 0.3065 g in ~15 ml of *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for ~5 h. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Reactions of 2,3-hexanedione with 1,5-diaminopentane in the presence of Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O and ZnCl₂ were carried out using similar procedure and macrocyclic complexes of the corresponding metals were isolated.

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